

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Extract of *Moringa oleifera* attenuates hematological parameters following salt loading

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ABSTRACT

Moringa oleifera Lam. is an important plant with huge medicinal potentials. This study aims at investigating the effect of leaf extract of *Moringa oleifera* on some haematological parameters in salt loaded albino Wistar rats. A total of twenty four (24) male albino Wistar rats weighing between 200 to 250 g were used for the experiment and were divided into four groups of six rats each. They were given either normal rat feed and drinking water, high salt diet (8% NaCl diet) + 1% NaCl drinking water and/or *Moringa oleifera* extract (600 mg/kg b.w., orally, once daily). The feeding regimens lasted for six weeks. After an overnight fast, blood was collected and analyzed for hematological parameters. The salt fed untreated rats had significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in red blood cell count (RBC) and packed cell volume (PCV), ($P < 0.01$). These parameters were significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced to near control values following extract treatment. Salt fed untreated rats were observed to have significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in total white blood cell count (TWBC) and platelet (PLT) count ($P < 0.01$), but the reverse was the case following extract treatment. In conclusion consumption of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract ameliorates the adverse effects of salt loading on the blood cells. Therefore, the extract is recommended to pharmaceutical industries for further research and possible use in the manufacture of drugs that are necessary in management of blood pressure and other related ailments.

Keywords: *Moringa oleifera* Lam.; Hematological parameters; Rats.

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INTRODUCTION

The quest for human survival, wellbeing and health care led to the recognition and discovery of many plants with medicinal value before the advent of orthodox medicine. These plants are said to possess components that are of therapeutic values [1, 2]. Among these many plants, there exists one that has almost all the nutritive values required by man. This plant is usually known in most literature as *Moringa oleifera*. The tree is native to India, it also occurs in different places which include Sri-Lanka, Thailand, Pakistan, Phillipine, Indonesia, Taiwan, Haiti, South

America, Caribbean and Africa (Nigeria) [30]. It is commonly known as Drumstick [3] and has several other names which include horseradish tree, ben oil or benzoil tree [31], mother's best friend and Nebeday. There exist 13 species of *Moringa* belonging to the Moringaceae family [4, 5].

Almost all the plant parts contain substances that are important for the synthesis of useful drugs [6] that can serve medicinal purposes, they also have important agricultural, commercial and economical values. The nutritional values of *Moringa oleifera* cannot be underestimated this is because proximate and

phytochemical analysis of *Moringa oleifera* leave extract [7] reveals that it contain important bioactive components which include carbohydrate, fat, protein and minerals eg. calcium, iron, magnesium, manganese, phosphorus, potassium, sodium, zinc and even water [8, 31, 32]. Others include vitamins (Vit. B₁, B₂, B₃, B₅, B₆, B₉, Vit. C, Vit. E and Vit. K), Carotenoids and antioxidants which include [7], flavonoids, glycosides, terpinoids, zeatin, quercetin and kaempferol [31, 32].

The antioxidant components of *Moringa oleifera*, basically Vit. C, carotene and quercetins are known to play major role in lowering blood pressure [33-35], quercetins and flavonoids can inhibit the production of nitric oxide and tumor necrosis factor by Kupffer cell when stimulated by injury [42], flavonoids also protect the cell against injury caused by x-ray and block the progression of the cell cycle and prostaglandin synthesis thereby inhibiting mutation and preventing carcinogenesis in experimental animals [43], the Vit. E antioxidant which is composed of tocopherol and alpha tocopherol is the most abundant and active component of this plant. This vitamin prevents lipid peroxidation chain reaction generated by free radicals from cellular and subcellular membrane which are rich in polyunsaturated lipid thereby preventing atherosclerosis and cancer [44, 45]. The Vitamin C components of *Moringa oleifera* can act as a scavenger of free radicals and do also regenerate Vitamin E indirectly [44], by virtue of this synergy, both vitamins C and E have attracted interest as agent that can retard atherosclerosis by reducing low density lipoproteins oxidation and thus preventing injury to the vascular endothelial cells [48]. Vitamin A is important for normal vision in dim light and for resistance against infection [13, 44, 47], the chlorogenic acid component of *Moringa oleifera* helps in moderating blood sugar level [36], the isothiocyanate component of *Moringa oleifera* also plays a major role in reducing blood sugar level in addition to its anti-inflammatory [9, 37, 38], anticancer and antimicrobial effect [39-41]. *Moringa oleifera* extract are also known to possess antitumor and hepatoprotective activities [9, 10], antispasmodic [5, 11, 12] and antiepileptic activities [14]. The antioxidant components of *Moringa oleifera* has been shown to protect against structural defect and also inhibit free radicals formation [15]. In addition, blood parameters like packed cell volume (PCV), white blood cell (WBC) counts, hemoglobin (Hb) and platelets (Plt) were shown to be enhanced following consumption of *M. oleifera* [16].

Taking cognizance of the enormous health benefit that abound resulting from consumption of *M. oleifera*, extract it is therefore very necessary to investigate the effect of this plant on hematological parameters following salt loading, thus the aim of the study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental animals

Twenty four (24) male albino Wistar rats weighing initially between 200 to 250 g obtained from the animal house of the Department of Physiology, University of Calabar, Nigeria were employed for this study for 6 weeks. The animals were allowed free access to their feed and drinking water. The rats were weighed before commencement of the feeding experiment and thereafter were weighed daily. Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Calabar, Nigeria. They were nursed under control of environmental conditions in accordance with international standard [29].

Moringa oleifera extract preparation

The aqueous extract was prepared according to standard method [17]. Fresh leaves of *Moringa oleifera* were obtained from Calabar municipality, Cross River State and were identified by the Herbarium in Botany Department. The leaves were washed to remove debris and were later dried in an airy-room away from direct sunlight to avoid possible damage to their phytoconstituents for two days. The leaves were further oven-dried for 30 minutes at the temperature of 40⁰C. The dried leaves were grinded to powder form.

About 1400 g of the powdered *Moringa oleifera* leaf was soaked in 7000 ml of distilled water for about 24 hours. The mixture was then filtered with a white cotton (satin) material, followed with filter paper (Whatmann No.1) into beakers and placed in an oven. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness using a rotary evaporator with temperature set at 50⁰C. *Moringa oleifera* extract was then collected into a sample bottle and preserved in a refrigerator.

Acute toxicity test (lethality study)

Acute toxicity test was done according to standard procedure [18]. Thirty six mice rats were used for the study. They were randomly selected and assigned to six batches containing six animals each. They were allowed a week for adaptation. Each batch received doses of extract intraperitoneally (1.64-104.48 mg/kg). Only the control group received normal saline intraperitoneally. They were all returned to their home cages and allowed free access to food and drinking water. The mortality in each group was assessed 24 hours after administration of the extract. The percentage mortalities were converted to

probits and plotted against the \log_{10} of the dose of the extract [18].

Salt diet and drinking water

Salt feed containing 8% NaCl was prepared by putting together 8 g NaCl in 92 g of the rat feed. Also 1% NaCl drinking water was prepared by dissolving 100 g of NaCl in small quantity of distilled water and volume made up to 10 l with distilled water.

Experimental design

Twenty four (24) male albino Wistar rats weighing between 180-240 g was randomly assigned into four (4) groups of six (6) rats each:

Group 1 (control): received normal rat feed + drinking water

Group 2: received same as group 1 + *Moringa oleifera* extract (600 mg/kg o.p. once daily)

Group 3: received 8% NaCl diet + 1% NaCl drinking water

Group 4: received same as group 3 + *Moringa oleifera* extract (600 mg/kg o.p. once daily).

The administration was done orally and the experiment lasted for a period of six weeks. Also the Helsinki declaration of 1975 as revised in 1985 was strictly adhered to.

Collection and analysis of hematological parameters

Blood samples were collected via cardiac puncture into EDTA capped bottles and the full blood analysis was done using automated hematology analyzer Sysmex model: kx-21N, Serial Number: A6695, as used by Archibong et al. [19].

Statistical analysis of data

Data are presented as mean \pm SEM. Data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and then followed by post hoc test (least square deviation). Data analysis was done with the help of computer software (Excel and SPSS version 17.0 for windows). P-values of less than 0.05 were considered as significant.

RESULTS

Lethality studies

Figure 1 shows that the LD₅₀ value from extract of *Moringa oleifera* was 1872.22 mg/kg.

Red blood cell count result

As shown in Table 1, the RBC count (10^6 cells/mm³) in the salt fed group (7.79 ± 0.31) was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) when compared with control (6.96 ± 0.13) and *M. oleifera* (6.71 ± 0.31) groups respectively but this was significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced in comparison with the salt + *M. oleifera* extract treated group (7.07 ± 0.12).

Figure 1. Lethality studies showing the effects of administering graded doses (200-3200 mg/kg i.p. mice) of *M. oleifera* extract against the percentage mortalities (converted to probits).

Hemoglobin (Hb) concentration

As shown in Table 1, there was no significant difference between the mean Hb concentration (g/dl) in the control group (12.74 ± 0.30) and the different experimental groups which are *M. oleifera* group (11.99 ± 0.69), salt fed group (12.17 ± 0.21) and salt + *M. oleifera* treated group (12.33 ± 0.30) respectively.

Packed cell volume (PCV)

As shown in Table 1, the Packed cell volume (%) in the salt fed group (46.32 ± 0.84) was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) compared with control group (42.84 ± 1.18) and *M. oleifera* group (42.23 ± 0.58) respectively, but this was significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced following treatment with salt + *M. oleifera* extract (41.76 ± 1.05).

Red blood cell distribution width (RDW-SD)

As shown in Table 1, the RDW (fl) in the salt fed group (37.21 ± 0.49) was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) compared with control (35.09 ± 0.94) and *M. oleifera* extract (33.07 ± 0.72) groups respectively but was significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower when compared with the salt + *M. oleifera* extract treated group (32.05 ± 0.67).

Absolute red cell values**Mean corpuscular volume (MCV)**

As shown in Table 1, there was no significant difference between the MCV (fl) in the control group (61.58 ± 1.22) and the different experimental groups which are *M. oleifera* group (63.92 ± 8.46), salt fed group (59.78 ± 1.66) and salt + *M. oleifera* treated group (59.25 ± 2.12) respectively.

Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH)

As shown in Table 1, the MCH (Pg) in the salt fed group (15.78 ± 0.77) was significantly lower ($p < 0.01$) compared with control (18.31 ± 0.20) and *M. oleifera* extract (17.90 ± 0.40) groups respectively but this was significantly ($P < 0.05$) reversed following treatment with the salt + *M. oleifera* extract (17.47 ± 0.39).

Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC)

As shown in Table 1, the MCHC (Pg) in the salt fed group (26.35 ± 0.83) was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) compared with control (29.76 ± 0.36) and *M. oleifera*

extract (28.33 ± 1.38) groups respectively but this was significantly ($P < 0.05$) reversed following treatment with the salt + *M. oleifera* extract (29.65 ± 1.18).

White blood cell and differential count

As shown in Table 2, total white blood cell (WBC) count in the salt + *M. oleifera* (10.85 ± 1.06) group was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) when compared with that of control group (7.77 ± 0.45), *M. oleifera* group (6.50 ± 1.31), salt group (6.88 ± 0.75), respectively. The differential cell count results are as shown in Table 1.

Platelet and platelet indices

As shown in Table 3, there was no significant difference between the mean PLT count ($\times 1000$ cells/ μ l) in the control group (639.67 ± 8.86) and the different experimental groups which are *M. oleifera* group (719.50 ± 60.52), salt fed group (479.00 ± 90.29) and salt + *M. oleifera* treated group (749.83 ± 41.11), respectively. The platelet indices results are as shown in Table 3.

Table 1. Comparison of the full blood count results between the control and other groups.

	RBC (10^6 cell/ mm^3)	Hb	PCV (%)	MCV (fl)	MCH (Pg)	MCHC (Pg)	RDW (fl)
Control	6.96 ± 0.13	12.74 ± 0.30	42.84 ± 1.18	61.58 ± 1.22	18.31 ± 0.20	29.76 ± 0.36	35.09 ± 0.94
<i>M. oleifera</i>	6.71 ± 0.37	11.99 ± 0.69	42.23 ± 0.58	63.92 ± 8.46	17.90 ± 0.40	28.33 ± 1.38	33.07 ± 0.72
Salt fed	$7.79 \pm 0.31^*$	12.17 ± 0.21	$46.32 \pm 0.84^*$	59.78 ± 1.66	$15.78 \pm 0.77^{**}$	$26.35 \pm 0.83^*$	$37.21 \pm 0.49^*$
Salt + <i>M. oleifera</i>	7.07 ± 0.12	12.33 ± 0.30	41.76 ± 1.05	59.25 ± 2.12	$17.47 \pm 0.39^*$	$29.65 \pm 1.18^*$	32.05 ± 0.67

Values are represented as Mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ vs control.

Table 2. Comparison of WBC and differential count result between the control and other groups.

	WBC (10^3 cell/ μ l)	L	N	E	M	B
Control	7.75 ± 0.45	$80.83 \pm .60$	13.67 ± 1.56	1.50 ± 0.43	3.50 ± 0.43	0.50 ± 0.22
<i>M. oleifera</i>	6.50 ± 1.31	$62.00 \pm 0.97^{***}$	$32.50 \pm 1.20^{***}$	1.67 ± 0.49	3.50 ± 0.22	0.33 ± 0.21
Salt fed	6.88 ± 0.75	81.50 ± 1.52	12.17 ± 0.91	2.83 ± 0.60	3.33 ± 0.33	0.17 ± 0.17
Salt + <i>M. oleifera</i>	$10.85 \pm 1.06^*$	$67.50 \pm 3.97^{***}$	$27.17 \pm 3.96^{***}$	1.83 ± 0.48	3.17 ± 0.31	0.33 ± 0.21

Values are represented as Mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ vs control.

Table 3. Comparison of the platelet count and platelet indices result between the control and other groups.

	PLT (10^3 cells/ μ l)	PDW (fl)	MPV (%)	P-LCR
Control	639.67 ± 8.86	9.18 ± 0.31	7.93 ± 0.16	10.72 ± 1.25
<i>M. oleifera</i>	719.50 ± 60.52	8.67 ± 0.28	$7.57 \pm 0.12^*$	8.83 ± 0.48
Salt fed	479.00 ± 90.29	9.33 ± 0.31	7.67 ± 0.08	10.12 ± 0.61
Salt + <i>M. oleifera</i>	749.83 ± 41.11	8.97 ± 0.54	$8.07 \pm 0.05^*$	$12.43 \pm 0.61^*$

Values are represented as Mean \pm SEM. * $p < 0.05$ vs control.

DISCUSSION

This research work was aimed at investigating the potency of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract on some hematological parameters in high salt loaded albino Wistar rats. *M. oleifera* contains numerous bioactive substances which include vitamins A, B, C, E, K, calcium ion, iron, potassium, proteins, traces of carotenoids, saponin, sitosterol, glycosides, phytate, flavonoids, kaempferol, quercetin, zeatin, alkaloids, steroids and phenolic compound. The lethality studies showed high value of LD₅₀ indicating that *M. oleifera* leaf extract has very wide safety margins and hence could be relatively non-toxic. This is consistent with the observation that certain products from these leaves find therapeutic application worldwide without any known side effect.

This study revealed that the RBC count in the high salt fed group was significantly increased compared with that of the control and those groups that received extract, in consistence with recent findings [16]. This increase was due to a high degree of dehydration following high salt intake [21]. Treatment of high salt fed rats with *M. oleifera* extract reversed the increase in RBC count induced by salt loading. It is obvious that increase in RBC would invariably increase the viscosity of blood, thereby leading to an increase in blood pressure and hypertension [22]. The ability of the extract to reverse this increase points to its potential effect in managing elevated blood pressure occasioned by increase in viscosity of blood following high salt treatment.

Although the difference in hemoglobin concentration among the groups was of no statistical significance, the PCV was increased in rats that received salt relative to other experimental groups, supporting the increase in RBCs. PCV is increased following dehydration, but this effect was reversed following treatment with *M. oleifera*.

In this study the RDW-SD was significantly raised in high salt fed rats compared with the control and extract treated groups. Increase RDW is an indicator of anisocytosis, hence high salt load could cause anisocytosis which was reversed following treatment with *M. oleifera* extract.

This study revealed that there was no significant difference in the MCV in the different experimental groups. Indicating that the cell size was not adversely altered following difference treatment. Nevertheless, the slight reduction in MCV of the group that were given salt points to the tendency for microcytic anemia. Also the MCH and MCHC were significantly lowered in the group that was given salt in comparison with control and extract treated groups. Low MCH and MCHC are indications of hypochromic anemia. Showing that high salt loading can cause hypochromic anemia, but this situation was

reversed following treatment with *M. oleifera* extract.

WBC count and neutrophils counts in the high salt group was significantly lower than that of control groups, but this effect was reversed following extract treatment, in agreement with findings carried out by [23, 24], which shows that *M. oleifera* extract boost the immune system. This is an indication that the extract is capable of stimulating the hemopoietic system [25].

The platelet indices results show that the platelet count was significantly decreased in the group that received salt compared with others. A decrease in platelet count could lead to excessive bleeding tendencies, purpura and leukemia which if severe may lead to death [21]. This tendency was reversed by the *M. oleifera* extract which is known to contain beta sitosterol that plays a major role in platelet formation [26]. The extract may contain thrombopoietin-like agents which are capable of stimulating the release of thrombopoietin [27] Pointing to the ability of the extract to boost platelet count even in deleterious situations like high salt loading.

The PDW-SD was found to be of no significant difference among the experimental groups indicating that there was no significant variability in size of the platelet, but the MPV and PLC-R were significantly higher in the salt treated group compared with other experimental groups. This result is of significance because MPV and P-LCR when measured have been found to be inversely related to platelet count [28]. MPV is mostly increased following platelets destruction. Increase in MPV and PLCR are implicated in the etiology of cardiovascular diseases.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion consumption of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract ameliorates the adverse effects of salt loading on the blood cells. Therefore, the extract is recommended to pharmaceutical industries for further research and possible use in the manufacture of drugs that are necessary in management of blood pressure and other related ailments.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. ANA wrote the first draft of the manuscript, managed the literature search, carried out the feeding regimen and analysis of blood, CON designed the study and wrote the protocol while OEO performed the statistical analysis and manuscript editing. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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